

SROC Serbian Radiation Oncology Congress

Abstract book

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Image guided radiotherapy for cervical cancer

Jelena Ličina^{1,2}

¹*Oncology Institute of Vojvodina, Sremska Kamenica*

²*Medical Faculty of Novi Sad, University of Novi Sad*

The challenges we face in radiation therapy for cervical cancer are primarily related to significant inter-fraction organ variations. Accurate tumor visualization and precise delineation of target volumes are also very complex processes. Image guided radiotherapy is of great importance in cervical cancer both for external beam radiotherapy and brachytherapy.

Simultaneous integrated boost and dose escalation at pathological lymphnodes became a standard of care for cervical cancer. The dose escalation requests precise contouring, optimal planning and more accurate patient set up and better quality control at radiotherapy machines. Computed tomography (CT) planning is considered state-of-the-art. Intensity-modulated radiotherapy (IMRT) and volumetric-modulated arc therapy (VMAT) have been shown to rise conformality and spare normal tissues. Daily use of cone-beam computed tomography (CBCT) provides visualization of target volumes and organs at risk. This improves the precision of radiotherapy.

As magnetic resonance imaging (MRI) provides excellent soft tissue contrast it is very useful for clear visualization of cervical cancer and precise target volume definition both for external beam radiotherapy and brachytherapy.

3D brachytherapy planning allows dose prescription to a target volume, not only to assumed geometrical distance. Co-registration with MRI is recommended for GTV (gross tumor volume), HR CTV (high risk clinical target volume) and IR CTV (intermediate risk clinical target volume) contouring.

Keywords: cervical cancer, image guided radiotherapy, external beam radiotherapy, brachytherapy

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